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Research Article

CHRONIC HEPATITIS C INFECTION AND HIGH LEVELS OF CIRCULATING N-TERMINAL PRO-BRAIN NATRIURETIC PEPTIDE (NT-PROBNP)

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Abstract:

Introduction: Liver Cirrhosis is the most common cause of hospitalization and deaths in the world. It is one of the most common cause of mortality and morbidity in the Pakistan mainly due to hepatitis C infection. HCV infection causes cardiomyopathy which results in poor contraction and relaxation of the heart that results in cardiac dysfunction and cardiac failure.

Material And Methods: It was a case control study held at Out-patient department and Medical Unit-1 of Lahore General Hospital, Lahore for a period of 06 months, from 1st January 2018 till 30th June 2019. Group 1 (case group) included all those patients who are HCV positive by ELISA. Group 2(control group) included HCV negative patients by ELISA. Samples were sent to FFH pathology laboratory. NT-proBNP levels were measured by COBASE 411 immunoassay analyser by using sandwich principle for vitro quantitative determination in human serum and plasma.

Results: Total 80 patients were included according to the inclusion criteria of the study. There were 32 (40%) male and 48 (60%) female patients who were included in the study according to the inclusion criteria. Out of 80 patients, there were 24(32%) patients who have prolonged positive NT-pro BNP value. The frequency of NT-pro BNP in patients in chronic hepatitis C infective and non-infective was 19(47.5%) and 5 (12.5%) respectively. The P-value was 0.001 which means that the difference between the two groups was statistically significant.

Conclusion: My study revealed that high level of NT-pro BNP was found to be associated with chronic HCV infection, which indicates that HCV infection induces myocardial dysfunction, such as myocarditis, in asymptomatic patients with chronic HCV infection. So, from above, further similar studies are recommended in our population to establish this fact.

Keywords: Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), NT-proBNP, Myocarditis, Cardiac dysfunction.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis is caused by hepatocellular injury by HBV, HCV, HDV, autoimmune hepatitis; alcoholic and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; Wilson's disease, alpha₁-antitrypsin deficiency and certain medications for example anti tuberculous drugs. Liver Cirrhosis is the commonest cause of hospitalization and death in the world. It is one of the most common cause of mortality and morbidity in Pakistan mainly due to hepatitis C infection [1-2].

Cirrhosis causes cardiac dysfunction i.e. myocarditis which results in poor contraction and relaxation of the heart that results in cardiac dysfunction which can be assessed by measuring NT-proBNP values [3].

The increase in NT-proBNP value is directly proportional to the severity of cardiac dysfunction. So it can be used as a marker of cardiac dysfunction. Previous studies showed patient with anti-HCV positive have increase NT-proBNP ($p < .02$) as compared to the anti-HCV negative patient ($p < 0.002$) [4]. Frequency of high NT-proBNP value in patients was 23(46%) and 10(20%) anti-HCV positive and anti-HCV negative patients respectively.

As high NT-proBNP value shows that anti-HCV positive patients are at risk of developing cardiac dysfunction, so a simple NT-proBNP test can be used to diagnose and prevent cardiac events in anti-HCV positive patients as it is simple, easily available as well as cost effective [5-8].

Objectives:

To determine the association between chronic hepatitis C virus infection and high level of circulating N-terminal pro-brain natriuretic peptide.

Operation Definitions: -

- **Chronic hepatitis C virus infection (HCV)** would be defined as patients who are anti-HCV antibody positive by ELISA.
- **NT-proBNP** cut of positive value ≥ 125 pg/ml.
- **Controls** would be defined as those subjects who are anti-HCV antibody negative by ELISA.

Hypothesis: -**Null hypothesis:**

There is no association between chronic hepatitis C virus infection and high levels of circulating N-terminal pro-brain natriuretic peptide

Alternative hypothesis:

There is association between chronic hepatitis C virus infection and high levels of circulating N-terminal pro-brain natriuretic peptide

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It was a case control study held at Out-patient department and Medical Unit-1 of Lahore General Hospital, Lahore from for a period of 06 months, from 1st January 2018 till 30th June 2019.

- **Sample size:**
 - Confidence level = 95 %
 - Power of test = 80%
 - Level of significance = 5 %
 - Anticipated population proportion 1 = 20 %⁴
 - Anticipated population proportion 2 = 0.6%⁴
 - Sample size = n = 50 in each group
- **Sampling technique:** Consecutive non-probability sampling.
- **Sample selection:**
- **Inclusion criteria:**
 - Both genders
 - Age between 20 years to 75 years
 - Cases: HCV positive patients by ELISA.
 - Controls: (Patients coming to OPD for minor illnesses like URTI)
 - HCV negative patients by ELISA
 - HCV negative patients by ELISA and without any condition which affect NT-pro BNP levels.
- **Exclusion criteria:**
 - Patients who have Hypertension
 - Patients who have already diagnosed Congestive Cardiac Failure.
 - Patients who are or had Myocarditis in past.
 - Patients of Cardiomyopathy.
 - Patients with Congenital Heart Disease.
 - Patients with Valvular Heart Disease.
 - Patients with Pulmonary Hypertension.
 - Patients of Renal Failure.
 - Patients of Sepsis.

Data Collection:

The study was conducted after approval of synopsis. All the patient were educated and an informed consent was taken. Both male and female patients of specified age group presenting to Opd/emergency room and admitted in wards were evaluated. Patients who meet the laid down inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Group 1 included all those patients who were HCV positive by ELISA. Group 2 included HCV negative patients by ELISA. Samples were sent to FFH pathology laboratory. NT-proBNP levels were measured by COBASE 411 immunoassay analyser by using sandwich principle for vitro quantitative determination in human serum and plasma. Results were verified by consultant

pathologist. Study variables were recorded on Performa (attached). All data was recorded by trainee researcher.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis will be done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Mean and Standard deviation was calculated for numerical variables like age and NT-proBNP levels for both groups. Frequency and percentages was presented for categories like high level NT-proBNP in each group. Odds ratio was calculated. Chi square test was used to determine the difference in NT-proBNP levels in two groups. P value <0.05 was significant. Effect modifiers like age and duration of disease were controlled by stratification. Post stratification chi square test was applied. Odds ratio was calculated.

RESULTS:

Data was entered and analysed in SPSS version 20.0. Total 80 patients were included according to the inclusion criteria of the study.

Descriptive statistics of age (years) of patient was also calculated in terms of mean and standard deviation. Mean age (years) in the study was 50.36 +_10.391 with ranges from 25 to 75 years, as shown in Table. No. 01

Distribution of gender of patient was also calculated in terms of frequency and percentage of male and female patients. There were 32(40%) male and 48(60%) female patients who were included in the study according to the inclusion criteria, as shown in Table. No. 02

The primary objective of the study is to determine the frequency of NT-proBNP levels. Out of 80 patients, there were 24(30%) patients who have increased level of NT-proBNP, as shown

In Table. No. 03

The secondary objective of the study is to determine the frequency of NT-proBNP levels in patients with negative chronic hepatitis C infection and patients with positive chronic hepatitis C infection. There were 40 anti-HCV positive patients out of whom 19(47.5%) were found with high NT-proBNP levels whereas there were 5(12.5%) patients out of 40 anti-HCV negative patients who were found having high NT-proBNP levels Chi-square test was used to compare NT-proBNP in anti-HCV positive and negative patients which was statistically significant (P-value 0.001), as shown in Table.No.04

Effect modifier like age stratification was compared with NT-pro BNP prolongation. There were 9(20%) patients who were found with high NT-pro BNP interval and having age between 25 – 50 years whereas there were 15(46.7%) patients who were found with high NT-pro BNP and have age between 51 – 75 years. Chi-square test was used to compare age stratification with NT-pro BNP which was statistically not significant (p-value 0.035), as shown in Table. No. 05

Effect modifier like duration of disease stratification was compared with NT-pro BNP prolongation. There were 7 (41.1%) patients who were found with high NT-pro BNP interval and having duration of disease between 1-5 years whereas there were 12(52.17%) patients who were found with high NT-pro BNP and have duration of disease more than 5 years. Chi-square test was used to compare duration of disease stratification with NT-pro BNP which was statistically not significant (p-value 0.002), as shown in Table. No. 06

Descriptive Statistics of Age (years) of patients (n=80)					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	80	25	75	50.36	10.391
N	80				

Gender distribution of Patients					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	32	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Female	48	60.0	60.0	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

States of NT-proBNP in anti-HCV positive and negative patients (n=80)					
		NT-proBNP		Total	p-value
		Positive	Negative		
Anti-HCV status	Positive	19 (47.5%)	21 (52.5%)	40	0.001
	Negative	5 (12.5%)	35 (87.5%)	40	
Total		24 (30.0%)	56 (70.0%)	80	

Odd ratio = 6.33

Age groups		ProBNP		Total	P=value
		Positive	Negative		
A (up to 5 years)		9(20%)	35(79%)	44	0.035
B (above 5 years)		15(41.67%)	21(58.33%)	36	
Total		24(30%)	56(70%)	80	

Stratification of Disease Duration					
Count		ProBNP		Total	P-value
		Positive	Negative		
Disease Duration		5	35	40	0.002
	B	12(52.17%)	11(47.8%)	23	
	A	7(41.1%)	10(58.9%)	17	
Total		24(30%)	56(70%)	80	

DISCUSSION:

Cirrhosis liver is defined as a chronic disorder of liver characterized by degeneration of liver cells followed by fibrosis and disordered regenerating nodules leading to portal hypertension and its complications. In 2001 cirrhosis liver was the 10th leading cause of death in men and 12th for women in the United States resulting in about 27,000 deaths [9-11]. In developing countries like Pakistan cirrhosis liver is more prevalent compared to developed countries. In fact both hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) infections have become endemic in our community.5 Both HBV and HCV viruses can cause chronic liver infection and can lead to cirrhosis liver, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and all other complications of cirrhosis liver with resultant increase in morbidity and mortality in these patients[12].

HCV related cirrhosis liver has become a major problem worldwide. It more often results in chronic state compared with hepatitis B virus (HBV). Almost 1.5 million new cases of HCV infection occur every year in US. The prevalence of HCV infection in healthy blood donors was found to be 15.6% in Africa, 1.5% in Japan, 0.64% in US, 0.34% in Canada and 0.075 in United Kingdom. Different studies from Pakistan show prevalence of HCV infection from 00-20.89%. Worldwide there are more

than 350 million of chronic carriers of HBV infection among them almost 75% belong to Asian subcontinent. In Pakistan the prevalence of HBV infection in healthy blood donors is 2-14%. In general population in Pakistan the prevalence of HCV and HBV infection was estimated at 3.6-18.66% and 4.25- 7.13% respectively. Alcoholic liver disease or alcoholic liver cirrhosis develops in 10 to 20% of people who drink heavily for a decade or more [13-15].

Chronic liver disease involves a process of progressive destruction and regeneration of the liver parenchyma leading to fibrosis, nodule formation and cirrhosis. It is the 10th leading cause of death in adults worldwide. In developing countries like Pakistan the prevalence of chronic liver disease is very high mostly caused by viral hepatitis B and C. Ascites, portal hypertension, oesophageal varices, encephalopathy, hepatocellular carcinoma, hepatorenal and hepatopulmonary syndromes are well documented complications of chronic liver disease. A wide spectrum of cardiovascular changes characterizes chronic liver disease[16].

In the present case control study, we found that the NTproBNP levels of anti- HCV-positive patients were significantly higher than those of anti-HCV-negative controls. HCV infection was independently

correlated with the NT-proBNP level after adjustment for parameters that might influence NT-proBNP. Myocarditis can be produced by a variety of different disorders, many of which are infectious. In the 1980s and 1990s, enteroviruses (coxsackie B and others) were frequently associated with myocarditis. In the past 10 years, however, other viruses, including HCV, adenovirus, parvovirus B19, and herpes virus 6 have emerged as significant pathogens. In these cases, the manifestations appear to be directly related to the presence of the virus. In fact, it has been reported that HCV was replicated in myocardial tissue of patients with myocarditis. However, in real practice, the clinical manifestation of myocarditis is highly variable, from abnormal electrocardiograms (ECG) of asymptomatic patients to fulminant congestive heart failure caused by dilated cardiomyopathy, for which there is significant difficulty in establishing a diagnosis of myocarditis because there is no established noninvasive “gold standard.” The invasive diagnosis method is endomyocardial biopsy, but the sensitivity of the biopsy for diagnosing myocarditis by means of standard histologic criteria is low, at 10–35 %, due to variability in interpretation and sampling error. In addition, in chronic asymptomatic myocarditis, in particular, symptoms are subtle or none. The importance of measuring serum concentrations of cardiac troponins and/or NT-proBNP to help diagnose myocarditis and heart failure has recently been recognized. NT-proBNP has emerged as an inexpensive candidate for population screening for heart failure. Beyond the potential to screen for structural cardiac abnormalities, recent data suggest that NT-proBNP is valuable for screening asymptomatic individuals to prevalent subclinical cardiovascular disease and/or incident cardiovascular events, including heart failure and cardiovascular death. In addition, among asymptomatic individuals, NTproBNP performs better as a screening test for future clinical events than as a tool to predict echocardiographic abnormalities. For outpatient evaluation, there is now a general agreement of a “rule-out” value of 125 pg/ml for patients under 75 years of age suspected of suffering from heart failure and 450 pg/ml for patients 75 years of age or over. In our study, all participants were under 75 years of age, and we found that 64 % of the anti-HCV positive patients had a high value as compared to mother study where it was 18%, whereas only 20 % of the anti-HCV-negative controls reached this value as compared to mother study where it was 1%. This suggests that HCV infection influences cardiac function asymptotically and that testing for NT-proBNP would be helpful in identifying patients in an asymptomatic state of cardiac failure[17]. It is still

unknown what causes the increased NTproBNP level seen in HCV patients. Another study reported that HCV was replicated in myocardial tissue of patients with myocarditis so it might be that HCV directly injures myocardial tissue. Second, we did not check ECG or do echocardiography; thus, we cannot report whether or not they would have identified abnormal findings. Furthermore, subclinical infection with other viruses could cause elevations in NTproBNP, which would increase the variability in this measure[18-24].

CONCLUSION:

My study revealed that high level of NT-proBNP was found to be associated with chronic HCV infection, which indicates that HCV infection might induce myocardial dysfunction, such as myocarditis, in asymptomatic patients with chronic HCV infection. From our study we concluded that there is statistically significant association of HCV with NT-proBNP. Therefore it is recommended to screen for higher NT-proBNP levels and those who are having positive NT-proBNP values should be strictly followed for development of cardiac dysfunction. Every possible measure should be taken to eliminate HCV. Further similar studies are recommended in our population to establish the effect of HCV as a causative factor in development of cardiac dysfunction.

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